

DETERMINANTS OF DIVIDEND POLICY: CASE OF THE PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR OF PAKISTAN

GUL ZEB CHAUDHARY¹, MUHAMMAD SOHAIL²

ABSTRACT

The dividend payout policy is one of the most debated topics within corporate finance. Many research studies have been undertaken to examine the impact of various variables on dividend policy. The objective of the study is to analyze the impact of firm-specific factors on dividend policy in the pharmaceutical sector of Pakistan for the period of 2009 to 2014. The dividend Payout Ratio is considered a dependent variable and the size of the firm, Sales Growth, Profitability, and Leverage are independent variables. The annual data for all the relevant variables are collected from the State Bank of Pakistan. The overall strength of the model is 45% and the model is the best fit at a 1% level of significance. The results of the study confirm that there is a significant positive impact of the size of the firm and sales growth on the decision of dividend payout of companies. Whereas ROA and leverage showed a negative impact on the Dividend payout ratio.

Keywords: return on assets, firm size, leverage, sales growth

JEL Codes: M50

1. INTRODUCTION

The dividend payout policy is one of the most debated topics within corporate finance. Many research studies have been undertaken to examine the impact of various variables on dividend policy. There are several theories and research work that argue different outcomes. According to Modigliani and Miller (1961), the company value is independent of dividend policy. On the other hand Brealey et al. (2008) argues that further research in the area of dividend policy is crucial to understand this issue in corporate finance. According to Lintner's research, dividends is very important for both shareholders and manager since it contributes to a higher value. On account of its importance, various research works have been done to determine what company factors influence dividend payouts. Many studies have explored various factors including Profits, Earnings, size of the firm, Sales Growth, Liquidity, Leverage, Market Capitalization, Risks, etc. Pakistan is moving towards development and capital markets in Pakistan are much more developed now and are growing faster than before. Therefore it is important for both investors and for companies to focus on exploring what are crucial factors that influence dividend policy. Moreover, according to our knowledge, not much work has been done in the Pharmaceutical sectors of Pakistan in this direction. This study will be an attempt to explore the impact of various company-specific factors on the dividend payout ratio of firms in the Pharmaceutical sector. The study will be confined to the period from 2009 to 2014.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Bongna (2014) investigated the relationship between the Dividend payout ratio with company-specific factors in the Polish market by utilizing panel data from 2000 to 2012. The factors include leverage, liquidity, profitability, and size of the company. The results of the study depicted that leverage, liquidity, and profitability have a significant negative impact on dividend payout. Whereas large companies tend to pay high dividends as compared to small companies.

Ali et al. (2010) conducted a research study to determine the impact of various factors on dividend payout. The study compared Pakistani companies with Chinese companies by collecting sample data from 55 Chinese-listed companies and 120 Pakistani for eight years (2001-2007). Their study adopted a multiple regression model (with a common effect). The dividend payout ratio was taken as the dependent variable whereas ROE, Size, Earning Management, and Self Finance Ratio were taken as independent variables. The outcome of their study confirms that the size of companies has a positive relationship with dividend payout in Pakistan and a negative relationship in China. Profitability (measured by ROE) showed up significant positive impact on dividend payout for both

¹ Lecturer, Department of Economics, Government of College University (GCU), Lahore, Pakistan

² Lecturer, Department of Accounting and Financial Economics, Government of College University (GCU), Lahore, Pakistan

countries. Self-Finance Ratio showed a negative and positive relationship with dividend payout in Pakistan and China, respectively.

Parsian and Shams (2013) worked out research in Tehran by taking a sample of 102 companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange from 2005 to 2010. They emphasized, along with several other factors, the impact of free cash flow on dividend payout. Multiple least square regression is applied to test the hypothesis. The dividend payout ratio is taken as the dependent variable whereas two new independent variables included are cash flow and systematic risk along with company-specific factors was leverage, sales growth, firm size, and current ratio. Their study revealed that free cash flow has a significant negative influence on dividend payout but the systematic risk did not show any influence on dividend payout. In addition, leverage and current ratio showed up significant positive and negative relationships, respectively with the dividend.

A similar study was conducted in Sweden in 2012 by Hellstron G. and Invagambaev G. By applying OLS and Tobit Regression models they attempted to investigate large and medium companies to check various determinants of dividends. The study encompassed the period of 2006 to 2010 with 38 medium and 29 large companies listed at NASDAQ OMX. Determinants considered for the study were free cash flow, sales growth, size, leverage, risk, and profitability which influence dividend decisions. The results of the study confirmed that Free Cash Flow influence dividend payout positively. Also, the profit and size of the firm have a positive impact on the dividend payout ratio. On the other hand, Leverage Risk, and Growth showed a negative impact on the dividend payout ratio.

Imran (2011) made another effort in this direction to empirically examine the effects of different variables on the dividend payout of firms. The focus of the study was the engineering sector of Pakistan. And collected sample for the study covered 12 years period from 1996 to 2008. Panel data for 66 firms listed at Karachi Stock Exchange from the engineering sector was collected for the study. Panel regression with fixed and random effect models was applied to test the hypothesis. Free cash flow, previous dividends per share, earnings per share, profitability, sales growth, and liquidity are found to be critical variables that have a significant impact on dividend decisions in the engineering sector of Pakistan. The results of the study confirmed that firm size, sales growth, and earning per share had a positive significant impact on dividend payout in all three models (i.e. OLS, Fixed Effect, and Random Effect Model). On the other hand, cash flow depicted a negative significant influence on dividend payout in all three models of regression.

Thanatawee (2013) undertook the study in Thailand and explored the contribution of ownership structure in the decision of dividend payment. His study examined the behavior of dividend paying of companies listed on the Stock Exchange of Thailand during 9 years commencing from 2002 to 2010. It was proved by his study that companies with more concentration of ownership probably had higher dividend payments to their shareholders. Moreover, it was evidenced that the number of dividends was higher with a more concentrated ownership structure. These results were supported by arguments based on agency theory. According to La Porta et al. (2000), there was the least protectionism of shareholders and thus more concentrated ownership in Thai companies which in turn led to more dividends payout ratios.

Some other studies focused on this area of association of ownership concentration with dividend payout in emerging markets. Baba (2009) highlighted this fact with the empirical data of Japanese firms listed on the Tokyo Stock Exchange. In the same way, Jeon (2011) proved the same phenomenon in Korean companies. Harada and Nguyen also found a negative association between shareholders' earnings and ownership structure. Based on empirical data collected from the Japanese Stock Exchange and accepted alternate hypothesis of the significant impact of ownership structure in determining dividend payouts. Similar results were indicated previously, by the study of Khan (2006) in the UK market.

Wang and Peijie (2013) investigated the ownership of companies concerning dividend payments. The study was undertaken in China by collecting a sample of all listed companies listed at the Shanghai and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges (SEE and SZE). Panel data was gathered from 2003 to 2012 from all selected companies. The main focus of the study was controlled firms thus sample data were categorized into 4 groups concerning various ownership types. For the study panel regression model was applied with the creation of dummies for each type of ownership category. Dividend payout ratios were kept as the dependent variable and the independent variable was ownership type (dummies). Other control variables included in the model were the size of the firm, market value of equity to total assets, free cash flow, and ROA. The outcomes of studies showed that there the influence of different types of ownership is different on the dividend payouts. As for control variables, size, Free Cash flow, and ROA depicted a significant positive relationship with dividend payments. Whereas the market value of equity to total assets showed up a negative relationship with dividend payments.

Patricia et al. (2000) confirmed the hypothesis based on the signaling theory of dividend policy. The study addressed the reaction to the initiation or omission of dividend payments for NASDAQ companies. The sample data for the period of years from 1976 to 1991 was collected for 69 companies that initiated dividends and 42 those companies that kept the policy of omission of dividends during the period. To test the hypothesis cross-section panel regression is applied and afterward, an improved event study was also applied to confirm the hypothesis. The results of the

regression are evidenced in favor of the signaling theory of dividend policy. Similarly, the event study also confirmed the phenomenon of signaling theory except for free cash flow. Specifically, in regression analysis CAR was considered the dependent variable. Changes in dividend yield and Free cash flow were used as independent variables along with a dummy variable of dividend yield. The results of regression showed up a significant negative association between Tobin Q and initiation. The results of the event study depicted the negative impact of omission on shareholders' wealth. Both results are consistent with past research work output.

Imran et al. (2013) documented various factors of dividend policy. The study focuses financial sector of Pakistan and 16 commercial banks were selected as a sample that is listed on Karachi Stock Exchange. The period encompassed ten years of data from 2000 to 2010. Ordinary least square regression was adopted to test the impact of selected independent variables on a dependent variable. The dividend payout ratio was set as the dependent variable whereas EPS, Size, Cash flow, and dividend of the previous year were included as independent variables in the model. The results documented that Earning per share, size of the bank, and current ratio influence dividend payments positively. All the outcomes were significant at a 5 % level of significance. However, cash flow is presented as negatively related to dividend payout. Moreover, the lag value of the dividend showed a significant positive impact on the current dividend payout ratio.

Zameer et al. (2013) conducted their research to inspect various factors in dividend decision-making in the banking sector in Pakistan. They attempted to make a comparison between domestic and foreign banks as well as Islamic and conventional banks executing in Pakistan. For the study, a total of 27 banks are selected and panel data is collected from the annual financial statements of banks for the period of seven years (2003 to 2009). To check the impact of various selected variables stepwise regression is adopted. Dividend payout was kept as a dependent variable whereas independent variables included the size of the bank, leverage, liquidity, profitability, agency cost, sales growth rate, risk factor, ownership structure, and lag value of dividend payout. The outcome of the study demonstrated that the dividend of last year had a significant positive impact on current-year dividend payments. Profitability, bank size, and sales growth showed up positively related to dividend payout. On the other hand, liquidity, leverage, and risk documented significant negative impacts on dividend payments. The study revealed the importance of the dynamic impact of previous year dividend payments on current year payments that supported the results of Hafeez and Atiya (2009), who proved the same postulate by using Latener (1956) model.

Maladjian and Houry (2014) undertook research with empirical data from Lebanese banks. The purpose of the study was to check bank-specific factors that contribute to dividend payment decisions for banks. The data sample of banks listed at the Beirut Stock Exchange from 2005 to 2011. Ordinary least square regression technique was utilized to see the influence of selected bank-specific factors including bank size, profitability, liquidity, leverage, growth, risk factor, and lag value of dividend payment on the dependent variable (dividend payout). Including lag variables lead to dynamic panel regression. The outcomes of the study supported previous studies conducted in the same area. Specifically, bank size and dividend payment for the previous year showed up a positive relationship with dividend payout. But profitability proved to be negatively associated with dividend payments. The study also suggested the stability of dividends over time to be thought about while deciding dividend payments for current years.

Ahmed and Yaseen (2012) considered in their research work, various determinants of dividend yield. The study was conducted with 320 non-financial companies listed on Karachi Stock Exchange. The panel data sample from 2000 to 2010 was used for analysis. The Lintner model (1956) (Dynamic Panel Regression Model) was applied to analyze the data. The dependent variable in the model was the dividend payout ratio whereas various company-specific variables are included as independent variables. In addition, the lag value of dividend payout is also included in the model to complete the model for the dynamic impact of previous dividend payments on current dividend payments. The results of the study described that the dividends of the company depend on earnings per share and dividends of the past year. The companies have a high speed of adjustment. Whereas the dividend payout ratio showed instability in smoothing their dividend payments. To investigate the impact of various factors on dividends, a multiple linear regression model was used. The results regression showed that the size of the company, more capitalization, and more profits of firms had a positive impact on dividend yield. Also, larger free cash flows influence positively dividend yield. Ownership concentration and liquidity also have a direct relationship with the dividend. But leverage hurts the dividend.

Fahim et al. (2015) investigated the financial sector of Pakistan regarding the issue of dividend policy by using an empirical data set of 7 years after the financial crisis (from 2007 to 2013). 53 conventional banks were selected as samples and panel data was prepared to analyze the impact of different bank-related factors on dividend policy. Panel Regression with Fixed Effect and Random Effect was applied with the dividend payout ratio as the dependent variable. Bank size, bank capital structure, liquidity, profitability, and slack (Investment) are taken as independent variables for the model. According to the outcomes of data analysis, all independent variables presented a positive relationship with dividend payout except leverage. Also, all the coefficients came up significant at a 5 % level of significance.

Rafique (2012) undertook research with a focus on the non-financial sector of Pakistan in determining factors of dividend policy. A sample of 53 companies was selected that are listed on Karachi Stock Exchange and annual data from 2005 to 2010 were collected from the official financial statements of companies. By utilizing a multiple regression model with dividend payout ratio as the dependent variable and independent variable including firm size, profitability, sales growth, tax, and leverage. The results of the study demonstrated that corporate tax and firm size had a significant negative impact on the dividend payout ratio. On the other hand, all other factors showed up a positive relationship with dividend payments but these results were not significant.

Parveen et al. (2014) performed research work in Pakistan and addressed the issue of dividend policy in the Textile sectors of Pakistan. A sample of 20 textile companies listed at the Karachi Stock Exchange was selected and panel data from 1999 to 2006 were collected from the financial statements of companies. To analyze the data ordinary least square regression is applied with the dividend payout ratio as the dependent variable. Net income and previous dividend payments are considered independent variables. The results of the study documented that both net income and the previous year's dividend payments had a positive impact on the current year's dividend payout. The results were significant at a 5% level of significance.

Reham and Takumi (2012) examined the dividend policy issues in the Pakistani economy. For the study 50 companies listed at Karachi Stock Exchange were selected as samples and cross-sectional data for these companies is collected for the year 2009. OLS regression is used for analysis. The model contained the dividend payout ratio as the dependent variable whereas profitability, cash flow per share, and corporate tax market to book value are taken as independent variables. It was proved by the study that profitability, market-to-book value, and corporate tax influence dividend payment positively but cash flow represented negatively related to dividend payout. These results were significant except for the corporate tax coefficient.

Arif and Akbar (2013) investigated determinants of dividend policy in non-financial sectors of Pakistan from 2005 to 2010. 174 companies listed at Karachi Stock Exchange from the non-financial sector made up the sample for the study. A panel regression model was performed with common effect, fixed effect, and random effect models. The dividend payout ratio was kept at the dependent variable and 5 independent variables included profitability, size, tax, investment opportunity, and Life cycle stage. The results of regression documented that corporate tax and life cycle stage hurt dividend payout in all three regression models (common, fixed, and random). Firm size and profitability also evidenced a positive relationship with dividend payout in all three models. However, investment opportunities showed up variant signs in different models.

Boanyah et al. (2013) attempted to inspect various factors affecting dividend policy in the manufacturing sectors of Ghana. Panel data of 50 manufacturing companies listed at the Ghana Stock Exchange comprised a sample set with annual data from 1997 to 2006. Panel regression models were applied for analysis with dividend payout as the dependent variable and earning per share, profitability, sales growth, and liquidity were taken as independent variables. The empirical analysis showed consistent results. Earning per share, profitability Cash flow, and size proved positive impact on dividend payment in all three models. Similarly, liquidity showed a negative relationship with dividend payout. Hausman test supports the Fixed Effect model to be suitable in all three models.

Abraham (2012) conducted work in Australia regarding dividend reinvestment plans to the decision on the current year dividend payments. The period of study was divided into two subgroups concerning tax reforms: pre-tax reform (1995 to 2000) and post-tax reform (2000 to 2009). Dividend Reinvestment Plan (DRP) dummy was used as the dependent variable. Nine independent variables were included in the model (Tobin's Q, Size, ROA, Cash Flow, CR, Debt, and Period Dummy). Firms were divided into DRP and non-DRP firms and comparisons had been made among them.

Naceur et al. (2014) conducted a study to inspect dividend policy in Tunisia companies from 1996 to 2002 with 48 Tunisian companies. Latner's Model (1956) was implemented to check the dynamic impact of dividend payments. The dividend payout for the current year is considered a dependent variable whereas Earning Per share for the current year and dividend per share of the previous year were kept as independent variables. Other control variables were sales growth, net income, market-to-book value, firm size, and agency cost. The results were consistent with the study of Hafeez A and Yaseen A. (2009). It was evidenced that firms try to smooth their dividend payment over time.

Severin and Jardin (2011) attempted to explore determinants and their influence on dividend decisions. The critical element of their study was tax inclusion in light of asymmetric information on corporate governance. They supported the dynamic impact of dividends instead of the static one. For testing the hypothesis of dynamic impact, they utilized the Lintner model (1956). Their study was based on theoretical arguments presented by many researchers, and policymakers in the past. The main aim of the study was to provide a more detailed picture of the influences of various factors on dividend policy according to several different theories of dividend policy.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

There are many determinants found in past literature that are considered by researchers to analyze their influence on dividend payment decisions. These factors may be categorized into firm-specific or internal factors and Industry specific factors. The firm-specific factors include leverage, liquidity, profitability, size of the company, sales growth, earning management, current ratio, cash flows, earning per share, ownership concentration, capital structure, Tobin's Q, last year's dividend payments, slack (investment), corporate tax, life cycle stage, etc. the industry-specific variables included: systematic risk, the book to the market value of the share, market value of equity, market concentration. Based on previous literature on the issue of the decision of dividend payments by companies, the following model is developed. Five company-specific variables are selected that are more frequently used by previous research work. The model is utilized with some variation by several researchers, among them Ahmed and Yaseen (2012), Bonga (2014), Hellstron and Invagambaev (2012), Thanatawee (2013), Jeon (2011), Patricia, Besley and Wai (2000), Ali and Zafar (2010), Parsian and Shams (2013), Imran (2011), Wang and Peijie (2013), Imran, Usman and Nishat (2012), Zameer and Arshad (2013), Maladjian and Khoury (2014).

3.2. MODEL

$$DPO_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (ROA_{i,t}) + \beta_2 (SIZ_{i,t}) + \beta_3 (SG_{i,t}) + \beta_4 (LEV_{i,t}) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

- β_0 = Intercept Term
- β = Slope coefficients of Independent variables
- DPO = Dividend Payout Ratio for Company *i* at time *t*
- ROA = Return on Assets for Company *i* at time *t*
- Size = Total Assets for Company *i* at time *t*
- SG = Sales Growth for Company *i* at time *t*
- LEV = Leverage (negative relation) for Company *i* at time *t*
- ε = Error Term

4. METHODOLOGY

For the study, the panel data set is collected for 11 Pharmaceutical companies listed on Karachi Stock Exchange. Panel data analysis is the most used method of analysis at present in the majority of research studies. Since panel data analysis has more advantages as compared to time series and cross-sectional data sets, it is a more efficient and strong instrument in research. The panel data set is a combination of time series data and cross-sectional data. For analysis of data E-views software is used.

The subject area of study will be the Non-Financial Sector of Pakistan. Within Non-Financial Sector, this study has selected the Pharmaceutical sector of Pakistan. All companies listed at Karachi Stock Exchange are the population of the subject area. There is a total of 11 Pharmaceutical companies listed at KSE.

For the study, all 11 Pharmaceutical Companies are selected that are listed on Karachi Stock Exchange. The sample period is five years, from 2009 to 2014. The data relating to company-specific factors are collected from the website of the State Bank of Pakistan (from Financial Statement Analysis). The other source of data is the annual financial statement collected from the official website of selected companies. Panel Data has been formed for further analysis.

To analyze the impact of various factors on dividend payout, this study has utilized panel data analysis. With 11 Pharmaceutical companies listed on the Karachi Stock Exchange and annual data of 5 years, a panel data set is developed with a total of 55 observations. For statistical analysis the following tools will be used:

Regression analysis gives the relationship (dependency) between one dependent variable with one or more independent variables. Here we will start applying different regression models as follows:

- Panel Regression Model (with Common Effect)
- Panel Regression Model (with Fixed Effect)
- Panel Regression Model (with Random Effect)

All the above three models are adopted by previous research as mentioned separately in the literature review. Some of them are Ahmed and Yaseen (2012), Bonga (2014), Hellstron and Invagambaev (2012), Thanatawee (2013), Jeon (2011), Patricia, Besley and Wai (2000), Ali and Zafar (2010), Parsian and Shams (2013), Imran (2011), Wang and Peijie (2013), Imran, Usman and Nishat (2012), Zameer and Arshad (2013)

The Hausman test is formulated to assist in deciding between fixed effect and random effect approaches.

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we discussed data analysis applied to collected data to analyze the impact of all independent variables selected for the research on dividend policy. Our independent variables are the size of the firm, sales

growth of the firm, profitability, and leverage. The data is collected from 2009 to 2014 from the website of the State Bank of Pakistan.

For analysis, we have applied mainly three statistical techniques. These are descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, and regression analysis. In the following section, we made a discussion on each of the analyses one by one.

Here we have our descriptive analysis details which describe the features of data collected for all variables for all companies. Table I presented below depicts comprehensive details for size, sales growth, return on assets, and leverage as independent variables. Whereas the dividend payout ratio is the dependent variable.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	DPO	SIZE	SG	ROA	LEV
Mean	0.417157	15.06	0.136823	13.91021	0.413367
Median	0.344439	14.98125	0.132058	14.11	0.390066
Maximum	.960653	16.76524	0.433449	36.02	0.816568
Minimum	0	13.59513	-0.18878	-19.75	0.137871
Std. Dev.	0.361424	0.905718	0.141209	10.35238	0.161508
Skewness	1.418451	0.343651	-0.21874	-0.07151	0.332776
Kurtosis	6.277544	2.039425	2.87664	4.76942	2.243328
Jarque-Bera	37.58061	2.790176	0.413195	6.302597	2.031025
Probability	0	0.247811	0.813347	0.042797	0.362217
Observations	48	48	48	48	48

The table shows the average value of DPO is 0.41 that is all the companies on average pay 41% of their profits as dividend payments. The maximum value of 0.96 shows 96% of profits are distributed by one company i.e. (Weyth Co. in 2010). Whereas the minimum value of zero shows that several times companies did not pay a dividend on account of low profits or losses in the year. The average size of all the companies is 15 (measured in the natural log of Assets). There is a 0.9 unit deviation in this size which shows all the companies are homogenous concerning their size. Sales growth shows an average of 0.136 i.e. all the companies perform with 13.6 percent sales growth every year. The standard deviation of this sales growth is 0.14 which shows sales growth remains consistent over the period. The average profitability of all pharmaceutical companies remains at 14 percent of their total assets. But some companies earn 36 percent of the total assets as profit (maximum value is 36.0). due to this larger value, the standard deviation shows 10.35 which makes data have more fluctuations. A leverage mean value of 0.41 confirms that on average all the pharmaceutical companies have 41% assets financed by debt and 60percent by equity. A very low value of standard deviation (0.16) shows consistent behavior of companies in maintaining leverage levels.

Now we have presented the co-relation analysis to explain the strength of association among all the variables (dependent and independent variables).

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	DPO	SIZ	SG	ROA	LEV
DPO	1	0.267618	0.083283	0.065777	-0.20739
SIZ		1	0.164017	0.461589	-0.27998
SG			1	0.538462	-0.32633
ROA				1	-0.55365
LEV					1

The table shows that there is a positive but weak association between DPO and the profitability (ROA) of the firm. The value of 0.065 shows only a 0.6 percent strength of association between variables. This means ROA would have a very minimal impact on DPO. This result is also supported by the very low value of the beta coefficient of ROA (see Regression below). The association between DPO-Siz, DPO-LEV, Size-LEV, and SG-LEV showed up moderate strength of association with values lying around 30 Percent. However, Sales growth with ROA and ROA with Leverage showed up strong correlation of about 50%. This means these variables move together in the same direction.

This section put the light in detail on the regression analysis. Regression analysis shows how independent variables influence the dependent variable. In our research, we have shown how to size, sales growth, return on assets, and leverage impact the dividend payout ratio of a firm. As mentioned above in methodology, we have performed three analyses, namely, regression analysis with common effect, regression with fixed effect, and regression with random effect. The following section is devoted to documenting details for each of these analyses in depth.

Here in this section, we have discussed regression analysis that shows the influence of all independent variables on dependent variables. The Common Effect Model assumes that all the companies are alike, thus the impact of all

independent variables on the dependent variable in the same manner. While the effect of other variables not included in our model will be captured in constant terms. The results are shown in Table.

The fixed Effect Model assumes that all the cross-sections, in our cases, all the companies are not the same. That is the impact of all the independent variables is not the same for all the companies. Thus we take a dummy for cross-section. The following section presents results for the Fixed Effect Regression Model.

The result shows that with a unit increase in the asset of the company, there is a reduction of 1.7 percent in the dividend payout ratio of the company. The result is significant as the p-value is less than 0.01. profitability shows a negative impact on dividend payout (the value of the coefficient of ROA is -0.0014. however, this impact is very minute in magnitude. The dividend goes down by 0.0014 percent as firm profitability increases by 1 percent. This result is not significant at a 1 percent level of significance. So it can be said that we cannot reject the null hypothesis. Lastly, the coefficient of leverage shows a positive impact on the dividend payout ratio. With a beta value of 0.605, it shows there is a 6 percent increase in dividend payout ratio as the firm goes one percent increase in its leverage.

Table 3. Regression Analysis (Fixed Effect Model)

Dependent Variable: DPO_?				
Method: Pooled Least Square				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.635466	0.902315	2.920782	0.006
SG_?	0.017703	0.013568	1.304798	0.002
LEV_?	0.605941	0.184619	3.282127	0.0023
SIZ_?	-0.17	0.058997	-2.88149	0.0066
ROA_?	-0.001456	0.006201	-0.23473	0.8157
Fixed Effects (Cross)				
AAA—C	0.289897		EEE--C	-0.38631
BBB—C	0.09738		FFF--C	-0.06595
CCC—C	0.839974		GGG--C	-0.13791
DDD—C	0.037496		HHH--C	-0.67458
Effects Specification				
R-squared	0.457746	Mean dependent var		2.271824
Adjusted R-squared	0.444835	S.D. dependent var		3.146346
S.E. of regression	0.58545	Sum squared resid		12.33907
F-statistic	74.18098	Durbin-Watson stat		1.620476
Prob(F-statistic)	0			

The table above depicts the coefficients of all independent variables. It can be seen from the table that the value of R-square is 0.45, which means 45% of the variation in the dependent variable (DPO) is explained by all the independent variables included in our model. Whereas 65 % variation is explained by other variables that are not included in our model. The p-value of F-statistics is less than 0.01 which indicates the model is fit at a 1 percent level of significance. Now we turn to the coefficients of independent variables. The beta coefficient value of Sales Growth is 0.0177 which shows that sales growth has a positive impact on the dividend payout ratio. When there is an increase of 1% in sales growth, the dividend payout ratio would increase by about 1.77 percent. The result is significant at a 1 percent level of significance since the p-value is 0.002 which is less than 0.01. Size shows a negative relationship with the dividend payout ratio. This means large companies are inclined to pay fewer dividends to their shareholder as compared to small companies. This may be due to the availability of new investment opportunities that induce companies to retain earnings instead of paying dividends. The result shows that with a unit increase in the asset of the company, there is a reduction of 1.7 percent in the dividend payout ratio of the company. The result is significant as the p-value is less than 0.01. profitability shows a negative impact on dividend payout (the value of the coefficient of ROA is -0.0014. however, this impact is very minute in magnitude. The dividend goes down by 0.0014 percent as firm profitability increases by 1 percent. This result is not significant at a 1 percent level of significance. So it can be said that we cannot reject the null hypothesis. Lastly, the coefficient of leverage shows a positive impact on the dividend payout ratio. With a beta value of 0.605, it shows there is a 6

percent increase in the dividend payout ratio as the firm goes for a one percent increase in its leverage. of the intercept term value.

Table 4 depicts that the p-value is zero which is less than 0.01. This shows that in our case, we will prefer the Fixed Effect Model over the common effect model.

Table 4. Redundant Fixed Effect Test (Likelihood Test)

Pool: PHARMACEUTICALS			
Test cross-section fixed effects			
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	20.38831	(7,36)	0

6. CONCLUSION

The dividend policy has remained the focus of research for a very long, and still, it has been addressed by policymakers, investors, and firms. The objective of the study is to analyze the impact of four independent variables on dividend policy in the pharmaceutical sector of Pakistan. The dividend policy is measured by Dividend Payout Ratio. The independent variable included in the study is the Size of the firm, Sales Growth, Profitability, and Leverage. The study period encompasses four years from 2009 to 2014. The annual data for all the relevant variables are collected from the State Bank of Pakistan. For the study, mainly three tools are applied. The first descriptive analysis shows the feature of the data collected. Co-relation analysis shows the association among all the variables. Finally, to check the impact of all independent variables on the dependent variable, Regression analysis is applied. The results of regression confirm that there is a significant impact of the size of the firm, sales growth, and leverage on the decision of dividend payout of companies. The model shows 45% strength and F-statistics proves the model fit at a 1% level of significance. The research shows dividend policy is significantly affected by firm-specific variables particularly, the size of the firm, sales growth, and leverage. The research is, due to the availability of data, confined to the period of 6 years (2009 to 2014), it is recommended that future research with a larger size of sample by increasing the number of years. Moreover, the research can increase its scope by including more independent variables in the model. Thirdly, the research focuses only on firm-specific factors, it is suggested that other industry and macroeconomic variables be included to analyze their impact on dividend policy.

REFERENCES

- Aivazian, V., Booth, L., & Cleary, S. (2003). Do emerging market firms follow different dividend policies from US firms?. *Journal of Financial research*, 26(3), 371-387.
- Allen, F., & Michaely, R. (2003). Payout policy. *Handbook of the Economics of Finance*, 1, 337-429.
- Amidu, M., & Abor, J. (2006). Determinants of dividend payout ratios in Ghana. *The journal of risk finance*.
- Arellano, M., & Bond, S. (1991). Some tests of specification for panel data: Monte Carlo evidence and an application to employment equations. *The review of economic studies*, 58(2), 277-297.
- Baker, M., & Wurgler, J. (2004). A catering theory of dividends. *The Journal of finance*, 59(3), 1125-1165.
- Bansal, D. (2004). Dividend Policy: Its Impact on Firm Value. *Finance India*, 18(1), 264.
- Ben Naceur, S., Goaid, M., & Belanes, A. (2006). On the determinants and dynamics of dividend policy. *International review of Finance*, 6(1-2), 1-23.
- Bhattacharya, S. (1979). Imperfect information, dividend policy, and" the bird in the hand" fallacy. *The bell journal of economics*, 259-270.
- Black, F. (1976). The dividend puzzle. *The journal of portfolio management*, 2(2), 5-8.
- D'souza, J., & Saxena, A. K. (1999). Agency cost, market risk, investment opportunities and dividend policy—an international perspective. *Managerial Finance*, 25(6), 35-43.
- DeAngelo, H., DeAngelo, L., & Skinner, D. J. (2004). Are dividends disappearing? Dividend concentration and the consolidation of earnings. *Journal of financial economics*, 72(3), 425-456.
- DeAngelo, H., DeAngelo, L., & Stulz, R. M. (2006). Dividend policy and the earned/contributed capital mix: a test of the life-cycle theory. *Journal of Financial economics*, 81(2), 227-254.
- Easterbrook, F. H. (1984). Two agency-cost explanations of dividends. *The American economic review*, 74(4), 650-659.
- Eriotis, N. (2005). The effect of distributed earnings and size of the firm to its dividend policy: some Greek data. *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*, 4(1).
- Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (2001). Disappearing dividends: changing firm characteristics or lower propensity to pay?. *Journal of Financial economics*, 60(1), 3-43.
- Gordon, M. J. (1963). Optimal investment and financing policy. *The Journal of finance*, 18(2), 264-272.
- Jensen, M. C. (1986). Agency costs of free cash flow, corporate finance, and takeovers. *The American economic review*, 76(2), 323-329.

- Kent Baker, H., Saadi, S., Dutta, S., & Gandhi, D. (2007). The perception of dividends by Canadian managers: new survey evidence. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 3(1), 70-91.
- Miller, M. H., & Modigliani, F. (1961). Dividend policy, growth, and the valuation of shares. *the Journal of Business*, 34(4), 411-433.
- Miller, M. H., & Scholes, M. S. (1978). Dividends and taxes. *Journal of financial economics*, 6(4), 333-364.
- Nickell, S. (1981). Biases in dynamic models with fixed effects. *Econometrica: Journal of the econometric society*, 1417-1426.
- Pama, E. F., & Babiak, H. (1968). Dividend policy of individual firms: An empirical analysis. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 63, 1132-1161.
- Von Eije, J. H., & Megginson, W. L. (2006). Dividend policy in the European Union. Available at SSRN 891035.